

Factors Affecting Career Shift: Towards A Focused Vocation Development

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ABSTRACT

Career shift navigates individual the potential for work opportunity that will lead people to better career of their choice tailored with the type of job, company, location, source, and salary. Work is the center of many people. It will come along with privileges, shift priorities, and becomes complication in life.

The study is focused on the factors affecting career shift: towards a focused vocation development. Specifically, it aims to identify the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, civil status, highest educational, monthly income (before and after) career, and length of service, factors that may affect career shift in terms of professional skills, valued interest, and opportunities, program of development on career shift, problems on career shifting and to know significant agreement between the profile of the respondents and the factors affecting career shift.

The quantitative descriptive research design is utilized in the study because it provides gathering of data, validates, explains, and describes phenomena in an organize manner. The study comprised thirty (30) respondents only. Purposive sampling is utilized in the study because this kind of sampling is also subjective, selective and judgmental in choosing the respondents to participate in the study.

Result shows that profile of the respondents' manifests challenging spirit in meeting the needs of their families. It shows that workers or employees who possess various skills will have more opportunities that will redound to success even if they seek career change. It shows that the program of development embodied various trainings and seminars and focused more on career change where respondents felt its importance and great need as it helps them in developing their positive attitudes toward world of work. It shows that career change is not advisable at all times because in the final analysis this may somehow turn out to be regrettable.

Keywords: *Career Shift, Factors Affecting Career Shift, Vocation Development, Professional Skills, Values Interests, and Opportunities.*

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INTRODUCTION

A career shift is the movement of a person from a job to another work depends on their needs and their interests. It will provide and pursue opportunities for their career in terms of ability, skills, and capacity. On the other hand, career shift navigates individuals the potential for work opportunities that will lead people to the better career of their choice tailored with the type of job, company, location, source, and salary. Work is the center of many people. It will come along with privileges, shift priorities, and becomes a complication in life. A career shift is not easy that fits a new lifestyle on how to work for career choice. It examines how to develop different ways in the creation of solutions in struggling, facing, and encountering in the job. Making options in their career ensures the future and the role of the individual in society, Yates, J. [1]. In addition, the value of having knowledge of career shifting helps individuals in their decisions in life as they prepare to explore the work of life. Useful information in career shifting equips individuals for a thorough and careful selection of work that merits them in their life, Mabel, Libassi, & Hurwitz, [2].

Nevertheless, there are many factors that affect career choice. They shift because of financial stability that can sustain their needs in life. They aspire for the best choice of career that makes them proud of themselves. Also, they want career shifts because of economic and social conditions to which they want a high standard of living. Still, this is due to the cultural background to where they belong, they wanted to work that can preserve their culture which is important. Nevertheless, they want to shift because they have experience with the job and wanted to share their expertise for their satisfaction. Anyway, still they want to have another shift of work because of their personality interest and their passion. Exploring the different influences of career shift becomes dominant to people who wanted to navigate life to the fullest, Malik, & Al-Emran, [3]. Consequently, it is important to note that career choice should start in choosing the course

needed based on the demands of the world of work. This can focus on the relevant career and how they perceive work as preparation in their job. This can be perceived through their benefits in education, integrated plans to reach their future career application. Through correct decisions and personal thoughts and inputs will strongly influence the learning process of career shifting which is important in one's life, Ray, Bala, & Dasgupta, [4].

Subsequently, the factors that influence career shift in terms of professional skills needed. Different skills can be applied to other jobs and can be modified and improved that fits different types of work. It also involves problem-solving and decision-making, sharing knowledge, and keeping the current skills. Being honest with colleagues, clients, and employers, aside from that being competent and being reliable producing a better output and better quality of work and deadlines. Committed and being accountable in words and in action. Utilizing the proper time management and usage in planning and skills on a daily basis and exhibiting a high emotional degree of intelligence in the people around him. Introducing the framework and theory on professional skills can be considered in these skills as an approach to better career shift in terms of employability, works, and innovation. It is a competency approach on professional skills, sets, and concepts for the promotion of career shift and choice. It is authentic and in improving the employability knowledge and skills as a catalyst of work experiences in career shifting, Ornellas, Falkner, & Stålbrandt, [5]. In addition, professional skills for career shifting produce potentials for individuals because they have knowledge and experience in the shifting of their career. Variation of skills can be considered and enforced in the career shifting considering the requirements of the work at present. This can promote innovation in their professional skills for a better career future, Custódio, Ferreira, & Matos, [6].

Moreover, the factors that may affect career shift in terms of valued interest when continuously searching for a greener pasture to sustain life. Believe that it is the fulfillment of life as exploring career opportunities that will make a person fulfill career. It will recognize an important factor in life and interest in a job or work. Willingness to work would mean valuing jobs in a flexible manner and accepting job privileges and opportunities and expectations. It establishes the approach and identification based on the behavior toward work. It is designed purposely for valued interest in the job and behavior. This is important in promoting valued interest in work, Ameriks, et al. [7]. Hence; it analyzes the effect of valued interest in the work determining the job and stress that would lead the person to a career shifting which helps in a productive work behavior in a positive way and work stress mediation, Farrastama, Asmony, & Hermanto, [8].

Certainly, the factors that may affect career shift in terms of opportunity vary in the work environment. Opportunity makes a man keen in the planning of career shift when feels dissatisfied on the work. Opportunity knocks at once, grab if there is a chance to do so. Opportunity can be learned and be applied by carrying it through to reality testing and only then can one evaluate the effectiveness of the efforts in a career shift. This can be utilized in many disciplines towards work behavior. There is a need plan for the opportunity to shift work identifying the specification of the job suited and expertise. Think, control, and know the benefits. Career development understands and better intends, and contribution to every individual considering the changes in the career and environment in the working area. It describes the changes and depicts boundaries and careers. It elaborated the sources of the perspective in the individual person. It provides personality influences on setting goals, and work values in the development of the career. The perspective of employees in different norms and various careers provides and promotes help in fulfilling sustainable work opportunities, Nagy, Froidevaux, & Hirschi, [9]. Despite career competencies, this will lead to the success of career and employability about their role in the society. It demonstrates and contributes to the professional opportunity in career and success, Blokker, Akkermans, Tims, Jansen, & Khapova, S. [10]. Therefore, management in a career should focus attention and practice to work values within the organization. It depicts and recognizes the importance of career management, process, and practices, de Oliveira, Cavazotte, & Alan Dunzer, [11].

Statement of the Problem

The study is focused on the factors affecting career shift: towards a focused vocation development. Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions.

- a) How may the profile of the respondents be described in terms of age, gender, civil status, highest education, monthly income (before and after career), and length of service?
- b) What are the factors that may affect the career shift of the respondents in terms of professional skills, valued interests, and opportunities?
- c) What program of development gave more focus on career shift?
- d) What problems are encountered by the respondents in career shifting?
- e) Is there a significant agreement between the profile of the respondents and the factors affecting career shift?

Hypothesis:

HO: There is a significant agreement between the profile of the respondents and the factors affecting career shift.

HA: There is no significant agreement between the profile of the respondents and the factors affecting career shift.

Research Design

The quantitative descriptive research design is utilized in the study because it provides information quantitatively tabulated in a form of a numbers continuum. It describes information on the profile of the respondents, factors affecting career shift in terms of personal concerns, valued interests, and opportunities in addition to the program of development focus on career shift and problems encountered on a career shift. Descriptive research provides a gathering of data, validates, explains, and describes phenomena in an organized manner. It discusses the key measures and concepts in a statistical research quantitative tradition to include the validation of the instrument inferential, and purpose of the study, Rumrill Jr, Cook, & Stevenson, [12].

Respondents of the Study

The subjects of the study are those employees who have been shifting their job from time to time for due reasons. They have been employed by more than three employers from different fields of work. The study comprised thirty (30) respondents only. The number of respondents assesses categorically the factors affecting career shift towards a focused on vocation development.

Sampling Techniques

Purposive sampling is utilized in the study because this kind of sampling is also subjective, selective, and judgmental in choosing the respondents to participate in the study. It is a non-probability method of sampling in obtaining a sample of representation.

Approaches in obtaining various samples provide evidence and viability of the population samples until it reaches the number of respondents in the study. Purposive sampling is a subset sampling convenient in choosing the respondents subjectively. It provides a method appropriate for the research. It fits to use because it is based on the design and representative in the actual size of the respondents under-investigated, Klar, & Leeper, [13].

Instruments Used in Study

The standardized questionnaire is used as an instrument in the study. Part I consists of the profile of the respondents as to age, gender, civil status, highest educational, monthly income (before and after career), and length of service, Part II collected data and information on the factors that may affect the career shift of respondents in terms of professional skills, valued interests, and opportunities, Part III collected data, and information on the program of development gave more focus on a career shift, and Part IV collected data and information on problems are encountered by the respondents in career shifting. The standard questionnaire is helpful in the implementation, design, and execution of the factors that affect career-shifting under study, Landfeldt, Zethraeus, & Lindgren, P. [14].

Validation of Instruments

The researcher conducted a feasibility questionnaire to a ten (5) group of people who have shifted their careers more than 3 times. Uses the test and retest method administering the test twice with a certain interval with the same group of people. The use of methods in observation provides tools for flexibility in the study. It is an instrument for tactical and technical analysis for purposes of reliability, mixed instrument observation, validity, and design. A reliability coefficient was then calculated to indicate the relationship between the two sets of scores that were obtained. The results reveal that the instrument allows obtaining information on the factors that affect career shift which is reliable, valid, and objective, Ortega-Toro et al.[15].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents

Age	f	%	R
25 and below	7	23	2
26-28	12	40	1
39-31	3	10	4.5
32-34	3	10	4.5
35 and above	5	17	3
Gender			
Male	19	63	1
Female	11	37	2
Civil Status			
Single	12	40	1
Married	8	27	2

Widow	5	17	3.5
Widower	5	17	3.5
Highest Educational Attainment			
College graduate	16	53	1
With MA units	3	10	3.5
MA graduate	6	20	2
With doctorate units	1	3	5.5
Doctorate graduate	1	3	5.5
Others:	3	10	3.5
Monthly Income (Before)			
10,000 and below	8	27	2
10,001-13,999	15	50	1
14,000-17,999	5	17	3
18,000-21,999	1	3	4.5
22,000 and below	1	3	4.5
Monthly Income (After)			
12,000 and below	2	7	4.5
12,001-15,999	13	43	1
16,000-19,999	8	27	2
20,000-23,999	5	17	3
24,000 and below	2	7	4.5
Length of Service			
5 years and below	19	53	1
5-8 years	8	27	2
9-12 years	2	7	4
13-16 years	2	7	4
17 years and above	2	7	4

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution on the profile of the respondents.

As noted in the table, the age bracket belongs to 26-28 years old, with a frequency of 12 or 40% among the respondents which shows that most of the respondents at this age are still shifting to another career for their stability. This determines their career satisfaction and burnout at their age in promoting their fulfillment in their profession, LaFaver, et al.[16]. On the other hand, Most of the respondents are male with a frequency of 19 or 63% among the respondents. This shows that male respondents are much attached to career shifting to find their satisfaction and stability in their work. Evaluation of male job relies on the dimension of works on their gender stereotype and role which is competent in employment sociable decision, Moscatelli, et al.[17]. Hence, most of the career shifters are college graduates with a frequency of 16 or 53% among the respondents. They are doing this because they have the qualification to shift from one work to another kind of work. Exploring the detail of degree and pathway will lead to a better work into focus and influence their pathway toward work in shaping their aspiration of career, Walsh, & Keary, [18]. Indeed, their monthly income before shifting is 10,001-13,999, with a frequency of 15 or 50% among the respondents. This shows that they are still longing for a high-salary job. In addition to that, the monthly salary after career shift is 12,001-15,999, with a frequency of 13 or 43% among the respondents. This shows that experiences and processes for looking for a job vary depending on the persistence, intensity, content, and dimension related to job success and search, and upon the needs of the respondents, Wanberg, Ali, & Csillag, [19]. Besides, the length of services is 5 years and below, with a frequency of 19 or 53% among the respondents. Length of services rendered remains a challenge among career shifter because of the stability they have in life, Kuivalainen, Nivalainen, Järnefelt, & Kuitto, [20].

Table 2. Factors Affecting Career Shift as to Professional Skills

Variables	WM	I	R
The respondents' employee believes that his various skills could be applied to other types of work.	3.37	MA	4.5
He believes that man's skills could be modified and improved.	3.63	A	3
Man wants to prove that he learns more skills as he practices other types of jobs.	3.80	A	2
To learn more skills is to experience different types of work.	4.33	A	1
A career shift is not regretful because of one's transferable skills that fit him to work.	3.37	MA	4.5
Average Weighted Mean	3.70	A	
Standard Deviation	1.41		

Table 2 presents the weighted mean and the corresponding interpretation on the factors affecting career shift as to professional skills.

As seen in the table, rank 1 is “To learn more skills is to experience different types of work”, with a weighted mean of 4.33 or Agree. This shows that respondents wanted to explore their work for their satisfaction. Rank 2 is “Man wants to prove that he learns more skills as he practices other types of the job”, with a weighted mean of 3.80 or Agree. This shows that respondents want still to prove their skills as they practice their profession. Rank 3 is “He believes that man’s skills could be modified and improved”, with a weighted mean of 3.63 or Agree. This shows that their skills can be improved for the better. The least in rank is shared by the two indicators which are “The respondents’ employee believes that his various skills could be applied to other types of work” and “Career shift is not a regret because of one’s transferable skills that fit him to work”, with a weighted mean of 3.37 or Moderately Agree. This shows that respondents prove that they have different skills that can help them in their career shifting. The overall average weighted mean is 3.70 or Agree which means that professional skills for them is important in their career shift. Respondents tend to manage their career shift by themselves that can bring them to a new challenge in their career. It expands and provides employment for better opportunities for them, Guo, Wang, & Wang, [21].

Table 3. Factors Affecting Career Shift as Valued Interests

Variables	WM	I	R
Man value most his way of living that he continues to search for greener pasture.	3.63	A	2
He believes that to fulfill his interest will make him a better person.	4.03	A	1
If a man feels boring in his present job, his interest to stay diminishes.	3.27	MA	4
If he comes across people who are fond of making intrigues to his life his tendency is to go to another job.	3.57	A	3
Recognition for oneself plays a very important factor in one’s life that if he is not recognized then he lost his interest to stay in the present job.	3.07	MA	5
Average Weighted Mean	3.51	A	
Standard Deviation	1.39		

Table 3 presents the weighted mean and the corresponding interpretation of the factors affecting career shift as to valued interests.

As noted in the table, rank 1 is “He believes that to fulfill his interest will make him a better person”, with a weighted mean of 4.03 or Agree. This shows that shifting of work would make him a better person to develop skills in the work. Rank 2 is “Man value most his way of living that he continues to search for greener pasture”, with a weighted mean of 3.63 or Agree. This shows that searching for a job will prepare the respondents for a brighter future. Rank 3 is “If he comes across people who are fond of making intrigues to his life his tendency is to go to another job”, with a weighted mean of 3.57 or Agree. There is a tendency for a career shift when the respondents are no longer happy with the work environment. Rank 4 is “If a man feels boring in the present job, his interest to stay diminishes”, with a weighted mean of 3.27 or Moderately Agree. This shows that a person uses the agency in the job whether enjoy or not for the reason to live the job. The least in rank is “Recognition for oneself plays a very important factor in one’s life that is he is not recognized, then he lost his interest to stay in the present job”, with a weighted mean of 3.07 or Moderately Agree. This is the reason why a person wants to have a career shift. The overall average weighted mean is 3.51 or Agree which means that valued interest in career shift is important to them. The stamina emotion of valued interest in a job explores and predicts attribution in identifying people who are flexible in their workplace, Brewer, [22].

Table 4. Factors Affecting Career Shift as Opportunities

Variables	WM	I	R
Opportunity makes a man keen on his plan for career shift if he feels dissatisfied with his work.	3.77	A	2
Opportunity can be learned and can be applied by carrying it through to reality testing and only then can one evaluate the effectiveness of his efforts.	3.53	A	3
To some extent, opportunity may be utilized in many disciplines because it can be used to explain vocational behavior.	3.37	MA	4.5
Job placement goes beyond opportunity and planning to involve the identifying of a specific job.	3.37	MA	4.5
Chance of opportunity begins when one encounters a problem, or experiences a need and realizes that a decision must be made.	3.90	A	1
Average Weighted Mean	3.58	A	
Standard Deviation	1.33		

Table 4 presents the weighted mean and the corresponding interpretation on the factors affecting career shift as to opportunities.

As observed in the table, rank 1 is “Chance of opportunity begins when one encounters a problem, or experiences a need and realizes that a decision must be made”, with a weighted mean of 3.90 or Agree. This shows that respondents may shift to another career for a better opportunity. Rank 2 is “Opportunity makes a man keen in his plan for career shift if he feels dissatisfied with his work, with a weighted mean of 3.77 or Agree. It is being emphasized here that respondents shift to another career because of low performance in the present job. Rank 3 is “Opportunity can be learned and applied by carrying it through to reality testing and only then can one evaluate the effectiveness of his efforts”, with a weighted mean of 3.53 or Agree. This shows that respondents’ wants to prove skills and capacity as an individual. The least in rank is shared by the two indicators which are “To some extent opportunity may be utilized in many disciplines because it can be used to explain vocational behavior” and “Job placement goes beyond opportunity and planning to involve the identifying of a specific job”, with a weighted mean of 3.37 or Moderately Agree. This is the reason why a person wanted to explore a career shift in life. The overall weighted mean is 3.58 or Agree which means that opportunity helps for a career shift. Seeking new opportunities sustains innovation to orient the goals of individual person, Chin, Li, Jiao, Addo, & Jawahar, [23].

Table 5. Program Development on Career Shifting

Variables	WM	I	R
A total family life program within the school curriculum with special emphasis on improving the care and motivation to assure positive impact of the home in the needs of youth.	3.40	MA	4.5
A career motivation program in school develops a positive attitude toward the world of work and creates a desire to be a part of the world of work.	3.90	A	1
A career orientation program provides all youth the opportunity to become aware of the many occupations open to those who prepare for them.	3.53	A	3
A career exploitation program provides all youth with the opportunity to examine and gain first-hand experiences with several career opportunities consistent with individual interests and abilities.	3.40	MA	4.5
A career training, retraining, and upgrading program for out-of-school youth and adults provide the opportunity throughout adulthood.	3.77	A	2
	Average Weighted Mean	3.60	A
	Standard Deviation	1.42	

Table 5 presents the weighted mean and the corresponding interpretation of the program development on career shifting.

As shown in the table, rank 1 is “A career motivation program in school develops a positive attitude toward the world of work and creates a desire to be a part of the world of work”, with a weighted mean of 3.90 or Agree. This shows that respondents are motivated for their career development in preparation for their work in the future which creates a desire towards the world of work. It provided them a positive attitude toward their skills to work. Rank 2 is “A career training, retraining, and upgrading program for out of school youth and adults provide the opportunity throughout adulthood’, with a weighted mean of 3.77 or Agree. This shows that respondents are totally shaped and molded on the values of their career at their tertiary level in preparation for their work in the future. Rank 3 is “A career orientation program provides all youth the opportunity to become aware of the many occupations open to those who prepare for them”, with a weighted mean of 3.53 or Agree. This shows that respondents when they are still studying are prepared by their constituents on the professional development of the job. The least in rank is shared by the two indicators which are “A total family life program within the school curriculum with special emphasis on improving the care and motivation to assure positive impact of the home in the needs of youth” and “A career exploitation program provides all youth with the opportunity to examine and gain first-hand experiences with several career opportunities consistent with individual interests and ability”, with a weighted mean of 3.40 or Moderately Agree. They are really prepared because they are being molded not only in the school but to their family and home as well for the importance of professional development of a career in life. Program development assessment on career aligns with counseling that enhanced work and practiced of the respondent’s job shift. The program responds to a greater emphasis among them. It is highlighted that greater needs in academics strengthen their career assessment, McMahon, Watson, & Lee, [24].

Table 6. Problems Encountered on Career Shifting

Variables	WM	I	R
Many respondents’ employees who made a career shift entail temporary setback in pay.	3.50	A	4
The cost/benefits of staying with a new employer turned out to be regrettable.	4.27	A	1
They were trapped in wrong decisions by not thinking that those negative aspects can be resolved around the work.	3.30	MA	5

Many respondents were convinced to go on a career shifts and it did not materialize.	3.53	A	3
Respondents had unpleasant experiences in career shift but can't return anymore to present job for fear of losing honor.	3.70	A	2
Average Weighted Mean	3.66	A	
Standard Deviation	1.39		

Table 6 presents the weighted mean and the corresponding interpretation of the problems encountered on career shifting.

As noted in the table, rank 1 is “The cost/benefits of staying with new employer turned out to be regrettable”, with a weighted mean of 4.27 or Agree. This shows that respondents’ regrets at the end when they have career shifting because of their abrupt decision. They should think many times before deciding to regret it in the end. Rank 2 is “Respondents had unpleasant experiences in career shift but can’t return anymore to present job for fear of losing honor”, with a weighted mean of 3.70 or Agree. This shows that they regret their shifting to another job because of their untoward experiences with their new job. Rank 3 is “Many respondents were convinced to go on a career shift and it did not materialize”, with a weighted mean of 3.53 or Agree. This shows that they regret their shifting of work because it did not work on their expectation which results in frustration on their part. Rank 4 is “Many respondents employees who made a career shift entails temporary setback in the pay”, with a weighted mean of 3.50 or Agree. This shows that they have problems with their pay and they need to adjust their expenses as compared to their previous job. The least in rank is “They were trapped into wrong decisions by not thinking that those negative aspects can be resolved around the work”, with a weighted mean of 3.30 or Moderately Agree. This shows that their decision-making in their career shift falls into the negative aspects of their life. The overall average weighted mean is 3.66 or Agree which means that they have encountered many problems in their career shift. It reflects on the shift construction career focus toward attitude in inquisitive work that constructively deals on perspective in life, Garcia, Restubog, Ocampo, Wang, & Tang, [25].

Table 7. Significant correlation on the agreement between the profile of the respondents and the factors affecting career shift

Variable	Computed r-value	Relationships *significant * not significant	Hypotheses *accepted *rejected
Age			
Professional Skills	0.002	not significant	accepted
Valued Interest	0.087	not significant	accepted
Opportunities	0.825	significant	rejected
Gender			
Professional Skills	0.167	not significant	accepted
Valued Interest	0.347	not significant	accepted
Opportunities	0.980	significant	rejected
Civil Status			
Professional Skills	0.016	not significant	accepted
Valued Interest	0.310	not significant	accepted
Opportunities	0.980	significant	rejected
Educational Attainment			
Professional Skills	0.228	not significant	accepted
Valued Interest	0.890	significant	rejected
Opportunities	0.379	significant	rejected
Monthly Income (Before)			
Professional Skills	0.134	not significant	accepted
Valued Interest	0.924	significant	rejected
Opportunities	0.934	significant	rejected
Monthly Income (After)			
Professional Skills	0.235	not significant	accepted
Valued Interest	0.837	significant	rejected
Opportunities	1.000	significant	rejected
Length of Service			
Professional Skills	0.205	not significant	accepted
Valued Interest	0.937	significant	rejected

Opportunities	0.695	significant	rejected
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Significant at 0.05 level, one-tailed test, df at 28 with critical r-value of 0.361

Table 7 shows the significant correlation on the agreement between the profile of the respondents and the factors affecting career shift.

When age is tested against professional skills and valued interest it shows that it is not significant because the computed r-value is lower than the r-value which means the hypothesis is accepted, hence when age is tested against opportunities, it shows significance which means the hypothesis is rejected. On the other hand, when gender is tested against professional skills and valued interest, it shows that is not significant and the hypothesis is accepted since the computed r-value is lower than the r-value, while gender is tested against opportunity the result is significant and therefore the hypothesis is rejected. Similarly to civil status when tested against professional skills and valued interest it shows not significance and the hypothesis is accepted while opportunities show significance which hypothesis is rejected. In addition, when educational attainment, monthly income (before and after), and length of service when tested against professional skills and valued interest, it reveals that the computed r-value is lower than the r-value of 0.361 which means the relationship is not significant and the hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected. On the other hand, when opportunities are tested against educational attainment, monthly income (before and after), and length of service, it shows that the result is significant because the computed r-value is higher than the r-value which means the relationship is significant and the hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

CONCLUSIONS

- a) It shows that employees from any sector are in their prime age which is considered the most flourishing stage of life. The profile of the respondents manifests a challenging spirit in meeting the needs of their families.
- b) It shows that workers or employees who possess various skills will have more opportunities that will redound to success even if they seek a career change. In their struggle to prove that more skills are learned through involvement to other types of jobs, they have the action done many times over skills. Valuing one’s interest in making himself a better person who searches for a job that is devoid of intrigues in his life.
- c) It shows that the program of development embodied various trainings and seminars and focused more on career change where respondents felt its importance and great need as it helps them in developing their positive attitudes toward the world of work and that they create a desire to be a part. These respondents believe that proper orientation with a proper career and a chance for opportunity.
- d) It shows that respondents developed strong keen awareness on matters of changing their job or transferring to another workplace. Along with this point, it is, therefore, safe to say that to go on a career change is not advisable at all times because, in the final analysis, this may somehow turn out to be regrettable.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- a) Respondents who are in their prime age regardless of gender and civil status should develop sincerity to their work using their skills and knowledge learned from various training instead of making poor use of them to create a good harmony with the employer and practice ethics for better working conditions. Since almost all respondents have finished their college and courses before launching a job, these respondents should serve as models for others.
- b) Employees should be endowed with the professional skills needed in their job to render better performance in the company without time wasted. If these employees come across with people who are fond of making intrigues to some employees in the workplace, they should be careful enough in their decision and properly weigh situation while applying ethics in themselves so as to hold on to the touch of professionalism to become a better person in valuing their interest most for a quality life.
- c) Program of development that is more focused on career should be strictly reinforced by the institutional organization such as family life program emphasizing positive impact of the home in the needs of youth and a career motivation program focusing on positive attitudes toward the world of work to career orientation program that provides an opportunity to occupations prepared by youth and a career exploitation program that provides an opportunity to gain first-hand experiences and a career training, retraining program for out-of-school youth.
- d) Employees should stand firm in their decision regarding career change for if they were trapped into the wrong decision by not thinking that those negative aspects can be resolved around the world.
- e) Since the profile of the respondents and factors in terms of opportunity resulted in a high significance which means that opportunity did not affect the profile of respondents. The employees should be reminded to let opportunity come into their life so that this factor may make them keen in their plan for career shift if he feels dissatisfied with their work.

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